

FINANCIAL GLOBALIZATION, ENVIRONMENTAL POLICY STRINGENCY AND CARBON PRESSURE IN G20 ECONOMIES: EVIDENCE FROM CS-ARDL APPROACH

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Abstract

The role of G20 countries in the sustainability of the environment is critical as they contribute to the world's economic output and the emission of greenhouse gases. This paper uses the Carbon Dioxide Pressure Index as a degradation indicator to analyze how financial globalization, economic growth, environmental diplomacy, and environmental policy stringency affect environmental pressure in G20 economies. It employs second-generation econometric approaches employing balanced panel data of 17 G20 countries between the years 1995 and 2024 to overcome cross-sectional dependence and slope heterogeneity. CIPS and CADF tests are used to evaluate the stationarity, whereas Pedroni and Westerlund cointegration tests prove the long-term relationships. The estimates of the long- and short-run dynamics are done using the Cross-Sectionally Augmented ARDL (CS-ARDL) model, which includes the interaction term to represent the moderating effect of environment policy stringency. Dumitrescu-Hurlin panel causality test is used to test causal relationships. The results show cross-sectional dependence, heterogeneity, and cointegration of the variables in the long-run. Financial globalization, economic growth, environmental diplomacy, and the stringency of the environmental policy raise CO₂PI in the long-run, which suggests that there is an increase in the carbon pressure. The relationship between financial globalization and policy stringency is negative and significant; stringent environmental policies reduce the negative environmental impacts of financial globalization. Financial globalization and policy stringency affect carbon pressure downward in the short run. The error-correction term (-0.31) is a measure that shows how a long-run equilibrium is established; the figure shows that about 31 per cent of the short-run disequilibrium is adjusted, which shows that there is a steady long-run equilibrium. The findings highlight that the policymakers in the G20 should coordinate financial globalization with strong, enforceable environmental policies and collaboration among the countries to bring about sustainable environmental policies.

INTRODUCTION

The concept of sustainability has become a critical issue worldwide as the problems of climate change, environmental pollution, and ecological degradation pose threat to human health and economic stability. The emphasis on sustainability among scientists and policymakers is predetermined by the increased global temperatures and worsening ecological situations (Ragadhita et al., 2026). The World Bank (2016) cites that environmental pollution resulted in a total of about 5.5 million premature deaths, most of which were a result of poor air quality. Besides health consequences, climate change would also be a significant economic burden and weather-related disasters already caused USD 470 billion in losses in 2017 and are expected to continue increasing in the following years (Giuzio et al., 2019).

To cope with these hurdles, governments and international organizations have enhanced collaboration in order to deal with ecological degradation. The term sustainable development was introduced with the World Conservation Strategy, which is spearheaded by the United Nations Environment Program that puts a heavy emphasis on the sustainability of natural resources and conservation of biodiversity (Clayton et al., 2012). This framework was officially laid down in the Brundtland Report (WCED, 1987), which described development as one that satisfies current needs without incurring costs to future generations in the process of satisfying their needs. Sustainable development, therefore, encourages economic development that is conscious of environmental boundaries, especially by maximizing the use of renewable and clean energy (Zakari et al., 2022).

The global environmental issues have promoted the multilateral collaboration in forums like the Conference of the Parties (COP) with agreements like the Kyoto Protocol and the Paris Agreement. In COP26, nations are pledging to cut carbon emissions by 50 percent of those in 2010 (Smil, 2022; Meng et al., 2022), whereas COP27 focuses on the collective action toward carbon neutrality (Rizwanullah et al., 2022). These activities showcase the increased relevance of the

concept of environmental diplomacy that incorporates international negotiations and agreements to address the issue of environmental transboundary (Ewane et al., 2023; Atisa, 2023). This diplomatic position is especially important in the Group of Twenty (G20), the countries of which constitute about 85 percent of world GDP and almost 80 percent of the greenhouse gas emissions (Asif et al., 2025).

Although there is greater coordination of policies and environmental efforts by the G20 countries, there has been an escalation of environmental degradation. The carbon dioxide (CO₂) emissions are often used as the most critical parameter of the environmental quality of different regions in numerous empirical studies; still, CO₂ only represents the pollution of the atmosphere and does not reflect the ecological ability of nature to absorb the emissions (Solarin & Bello, 2018; Wu et al., 2019). This is especially important to the high-emission economies, including the United States, which is still among the largest CO₂ emitters in the world, despite its highly developed economy (Haciimamoglu and Sungur, 2024). Measuring the environmental sustainability only in terms of emissions is thus a partial evaluation of the environmental pressure (Akbar et al., 2025).

In order to fill this gap, this paper uses the Carbon Pressure Index (CO₂PI) as the fundamental indicator of environmental degradation. CO₂PI refers to the proportion of carbon dioxide emissions against biocapacity and it represents the degree to which man-made carbon emissions surpass the natural rate of biocapacity regeneration (Wackernagel and Rees, 1998; Akadiri et al., 2022). CO₂PI provides a more detailed measure of environmental stress than that provided by CO₂ emissions because it combines emission demand with ecological supply. In this regard, the paper will analyze how economic development, financial globalization, environmental diplomacy and the stringency of environmental policy impact the G20 countries on carbon pressure. The conclusions are expected to offer evidence-based information to policymakers, diplomats, and other

environmental stakeholders who want to enhance collaboration on the international level and exist in a sustainable environment.

The rest of this paper will be structured in the following way. Section 2 includes the literature review and Section 3 will include the theoretical framework. The data, model, and methodology are outlined in Section 4. The empirical findings are reported and discussed in Section 5. Section 6 is the summary of the study and provides policy suggestions and constraints.

2. Literature Review

The role of environmental diplomacy, policy effectiveness, and the impacts of financial globalization on ecological sustainability has become more and more the subject of emphasis with reference to environmental concerns, public awareness, and policy requirements. The traditional indicators of degradation have dominated the previous studies in an attempt to determine the impacts of economic growth, financial globalization, and the stringency of the policy on the environmental outcomes. The analysis provides the studies that use Carbon Pressure Index (CO2PI) or similar constructs, such as the Ecological Footprint Pressure Index or Load Capacity Factor, because these measures a combination of emissions and ecological capacity, and are a more holistic measure of environmental pressure created by humans (Wackernagel and Rees, 1998; Wang et al., 2018).

Environmental Degradation and Economic Growth:

Carbon pressure is affected by the economic growth due to scale, composition, and technique impacts (Grossman and Krueger, 1996). Although growth may promote livelihood and cleaner production processes, it tends to raise emissions in relation to the ecological capacity, which increases the CO2PI. Research has pointed to a variety of interrelations: Pata et al. (2022) found that the relationship between economic growth and EFPI in India was of a U-shaped type, and Baloch et al. (2019) and Alnemer et al. (2023) emphasized the

environmental disadvantages of urbanization and fossil-based modernization. Latif and Faridi (2023), Akadiri et al. (2022) and Gyamfi et al. (2023) also show that the growth in the GDP is frequently related to the CO2 emissions, especially in situations when a low level of clean energy is adopted. On the other hand, studies carried out in OECD and BRICS countries indicate inconsistent findings, where some articles indicate that GDP may decrease the environmental pressure based on specific circumstances (Guloglu et al., 2023; Adebayo and Samour, 2024). These results point to the necessity of considering both the growth and technological/policy alleviation when assessing the carbon pressure.

Carbon Pressure and Financial Globalization:

Financial globalization (FG), including foreign direct investment, portfolio flows and international financial integration, influences environmental pressure in two counter mechanisms. On the one hand, FG helps in transferring technology and making resources effective, which may decrease CO2PI (Zheng et al., 2023). Conversely, in the absence of strong regulatory systems, FG may encourage the outsourcing of polluting industries to reduce regulation, resulting in carbon pressure, as proposed by the pollution haven hypothesis (Prempeh, 2024; Wang et al., 2023). Some of the earlier researches provide conflicting evidence, with a particular part of the literature demonstrating environmental improvement (Akadiri et al., 2022; Raihan et al., 2023) and another part of the literature demonstrating deterioration (Ibrahim et al., 2024; Liu et al., 2024). It seems that the overall impact of FG on CO2PI is dependent on whether domestic environmental regulations are in place and whether they are stringent.

Environmental Degradation and Environmental Policy Stringency:

Stringency of the Environmental Policy (EPS) is used to assess the price on the activities that are harmful to the environment and the strength of the environmental regulations. High EPS promotes the use of green technologies and

efficient production methods, which mitigates the carbon pressure (Porter et al., 1995; Albulescu et al., 2022). Nevertheless, empirical research results are rather ambiguous. EPS has decreased emissions in BRICS countries (Dai and Du, 2023), but the effect of strict measures can be the green paradox, where ecologically friendly policies can sometimes lead to an increase or deterioration in the desire to invest in it (Rufael, 2021; Hao et al., 2018). These contradictory findings underscore the relevance of contextual factors such as institutional quality and mechanisms of compliance in defining whether EPS will be effective on CO₂PI.

Environmental Degradation and Environmental Diplomacy:

Through environmental diplomacy, countries can also work together across borders to resolve international environmental challenges such as climate change, pollution, and resource depletion. Such agreements as the Paris Agreement put the principle of Common but Differentiated Responsibilities (CBDR) into practice, balancing the interests of developed and developing countries (Rizwanullah et al., 2024). There has been an indication that carbon pressure may be mitigated by the use of effective environmental diplomacy that involves coordinated emission cuts, transfer of technology, and international best practices (Nasrullah et al., 2021; Khan and Hou, 2021). However, this may be compromised by the fact that compliance gaps and uneven application of treaties can take place, especially in the third world countries.

Although there is a lot of literature on economic growth, financial globalization, EPS, and environmental diplomacy, not many studies use CO₂PI as a dependent variable. Moreover, the moderating value of EPS in the correlation between FG and carbon pressure, the impact of environmental diplomacy, is not properly studied. The paper tries to fill these gaps by looking at the G20 countries in terms of CO₂PI as a measure to compare the overall impact of economic, financial, regulatory, and diplomatic factors on environmental degradation.

3. Theoretical Framework

This study has three main strands in its theoretical basis: the influence of economic growth on the pressure of carbon, the influence of financial globalization, which is mitigated by the stringency of environmental policy, and the impact of environmental diplomacy. The scale, composition and technique effects of economic growth are related to CO₂PI (Grossman and Krueger, 1996). Scale effect: The increased production and consumption increase emissions in comparison with biocapacity, and elevate CO₂PI. Composition effect: The intensity of pollution is a factor of the structure of the industry; economies that are dependent on carbon-intensive industries have a greater CO₂PI. Technique effect: The use of cleaner technologies and efficiency gains decreases CO₂PI, especially in those countries with robust regulations.

In developing nations, economic pressures tend to give preference to growth rather than environmental sustainability, and the increased carbon pressure, but in developed economies, CO₂PI is minimized by technology and strict environmental regulations.

FG has a positive as well as a negative effect on CO₂PI. Capital inflows and FDI can introduce cleaner technologies that enhance resource efficiency and reduce carbon pressure. On the other hand, lax regulatory systems facilitate the pollution haven phenomenon, which raises CO₂PI. The overall effect is highly conditioned by the strictness of the environmental policies, which may compel the companies to be greener and less pressured by carbon.

The cost of pollution to the regulation is measured through EPS in the form of an index by the OECD. The Porter Hypothesis says that tougher regulations encourage innovation, cleaner production, and better operational efficiency and therefore lower CO₂PI. EPS also mediates the environmental consequences of financial globalization: the high EPS softens the possible adverse impact of FDI on carbon pressure, whereas the weak EPS reinforces it.

Environmental diplomacy involves international collaboration towards dealing with transboundary environmental issues. Ecological diplomacy

decreases CO₂PI by encouraging emission mitigation pacts, technology transfers, and consistency in sustainable norms, by utilizing nationwide strategies in line with the environment. The integration of CO₂PI into diplomacy assessment enables nations, especially in the G20, to tune policies based on environmental capacity and the level of development.

According to this theoretical framework, CO₂PI depends on economic growth, financial globalization, and environmental diplomacy and EPS mediate the impact of FG on carbon pressure. The use of CO₂PI as the dependent variable facilitates a compound evaluation of the anthropogenic emissions of carbon on the ecological capacity, hence giving a sound background to the hypotheses and empirical model of the study.

4. Econometric Methods

4.1 Data

This study intends to explore and define the role of macroeconomic drivers like financial globalization (FG), Environmental Diplomacy (ED), Gross Domestic Product (GDP), and Environmental Policy Stringency (EPS) in climate mitigation efforts. The study is still investigating the moderating role of Environmental Policy Stringency (EPS) in the setting of financial globalization (FG) in terms of Carbon Dioxide Pressure Index (CO₂PI) over a period of 30 years between 1995 and 2024. It targets the selected G20 countries such as Australia, Brazil, Canada, China, France, Germany, India, Indonesia, Italy, Japan, South Korea, Mexico, Russia, South Africa, Turkey, the United Kingdom, and the United States. In this respect, it should be stated that Argentina and Saudi Arabia were not included in the study because of the lack of data. The information concerning the investigated economic indicators is obtained from the World Bank, Global Footprint Network, International Monetary Fund (IMF), OECD and KOF Index. All the data were converted into the form of the natural logarithm to lessen the chances of data irregularities and heteroscedasticity. A summary of the study variables has been given in Table 1,

whereby each variable has been identified with its symbols, measurement, and data sources.

4.2 Model Specifications

Based on the existing literature, an econometric model used in the study was selected and it incorporated the framework developed by Chishti and Dogan(2024) to determine the top ten countries with high consumption of renewable energy. Nonetheless, this study attempts to introduce certain economic indicators and explore the moderating effect of Environmental Policy Stringency as an attempt to explain the linkages between the variables under consideration. The model has a functional structure that has been created to demonstrate the overall purpose of our investigation.

CO₂PI = f (FG, ED, GDP, EPS, EPS*FG)

$$\text{CO}_2\text{PI}_{it} = \alpha_{lit} + \alpha_{fit} \text{FG}_{it} + \alpha_{eit} \text{ED}_{it} + \alpha_{git} \text{GDP}_{it} + \alpha_{epit} \text{EPS}_{it} + \alpha_{efit} \text{EPS} * \text{FG}_{it} + \epsilon_{it} \quad (i)$$

The dependent variable of this model is the Carbon Pressure Index (CO₂PI), whereas the independent variables are financial globalization (FG), Environmental Diplomacy (ED), Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and Environmental Policy Stringency (EPS). A moderating term, EPS FG, has been included to evaluate the moderating actions of EPS and FG. The error term ϵ is an idiosyncratic error, which is independent and identically distributed, and follows the standard assumption of being normally distributed with a mean of zero and a constant variance.

In this context, i denotes the countries under consideration, t indicates the period, and α_{lit} represents the intercept. The parameters α_{fit} , α_{eit} , α_{git} , α_{epit} , and α_{efit} correspond to the long-run elasticity estimates of CO₂PI concerning the variables FG, ED, GDP, EPS, and the interaction term (EPS*FG), respectively.

4.3 Methodology

This research used various econometric tools that have been particularly applied to panel data. Since cross-sectional dependence (CD) also remains a major problem in this field, the study first started by running tests for CD. After that,

unit root tests were performed to examine the stationarity of the variables, followed by a cointegration test to see if the series have any long-run relationships with each other. The cross-sectional augmented autoregressive distributive lag (CS-ARDL) approach was used to look at the links that exist among the selected variables for the analyzed countries. Finally, the panel heterogeneous causality test was undertaken to check the causal relationships that exist among the variables under analysis.

The current study tries to find relationships both short-term and long-term between the variables of focus. Additionally, it aims to emphasize the moderating effects that exist among these variables. The study further aims to examine causal relations of economic indicators in selected G20 countries over the period from 1995 up to 2024, including Australia, Brazil, Canada, China, France, Germany, India, Indonesia, Italy, Japan, South Korea, Mexico, Russia, South Africa, Turkey, the UK, and the United States. This is now an increasingly interdependent world, facilitated by advances in information and communications technology, digital marketing, and multiple social media platforms. In this regard, the nations are more united than ever. Several factors have thus led to the creation of an atmosphere of interdependence within nations, such as uneven population distribution, income-based classifications of countries, labor shortages and surpluses, demographic aging, and uneven distribution of natural resources. Such collaboration in the form of dealing with climatic changes and other futuristic economic barriers in working toward achieving the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals by 2030 is largely required, as it is possible for a country's outputs to change the outcomes of the world at large. This interdependence is especially prevalent in G20 countries, which are highly interlinked with one another in their pursuits toward sustainable development. The econometrician has termed this phenomenon as cross-sectional dependence (CSD).

In the study, there are four commonly accepted tests to confirm cross-sectional dependence.

These include the CD test developed by Pesaran (2007), the BP Lagrange Multiplier (LM) test introduced by Breusch and Pagan (1980), the scaled LM test proposed by Pesaran (2007), and finally, the bias-corrected scaled LM test formulated by Baltagi et al. (2012).

Furthermore, this research incorporates the slope heterogeneity test across the series to assess the presence of heterogeneity. Subsequently, the focus shifted to analyzing the stationary properties of each chosen variable. The stationary process is evaluated through the application of second-generation augmented cross-sectional panel unit root tests, specifically the CIPS and CADF tests introduced by Pesaran et al. (2004). Following the validation of the cross-sectional dependence (CSD) and the stationary characteristics, the next phase involves investigating the cointegration among the variables. To achieve this, the study uses methodologies suggested by Pedroni (2004) and Westerlund (2007) to determine whether there exists a long-term relation among the variables considered in the sample.

The first author that developed the cointegration test is Pedroni, which would then be applied to check if a process is stationary or not. The Pedroni cointegration test is a residual-based test accounting for short-term dynamics and slope coefficients in the long run and is different between panel members. This test had constituted within-dimension pooled tests and group mean between-dimension tests. Further, it carried individual heterogeneous fixed effects and trend components (Pedroni, 2004). Then on appropriate for situations that arise with the existence of cross-sectional dependence (CSD), the Westerlund panel cointegration test was later on utilized. More recent research uses the cross-sectional methodology within the framework of the ARDL model to try to address issues of cross-sectional dependence (CSD), heterogeneity and to allow the potential mixture of integration orders: $I(0)$ and $I(1)$. The method allows easy estimation of short-run and long-run coefficients, and results come out to be robust as compared to conventional ARDL, fully modified ordinary least squares, and dynamic ordinary least squares

methods (Chishti et al,2024). The panel causality test of Dumitrescu and Hurlin (2012) was also conducted to explore the causal relationship between the variables. This is suitable for the

balanced and heterogeneous panel series used and presents an innovative approach to the set of variables selected for this purpose.

Table 1: Variables of Study and Their Description

Variable	Symbol	Measurement	Source
CO ₂ Emissions Pressure Index	CO ₂ PI	CO ₂ Emissions (mt Per Capita) / Biocapacity (Gha person)	WDI, GFN
Financial Globalization	FG	Globalization Index	KOF
Environmental Diplomacy	ED	Cumulative Treaties	IMF
Gross Domestic Product	GDP	Per capita (constant US\$ 2015)	WDI
Environmental Policy Stringency	EPS	Stringency Index	OECD

5. Results and Discussion

Results

The upper panel of Table 2 reports the descriptive statistics of the variables used in the analysis, including the mean, median, and range. The mean value of the CO₂ Pressure Index (CO₂PI) is 3.24, with values ranging from 0.26 to 8.32, indicating substantial variation in environmental pressure across observations. Financial globalization (FG) has a comparatively stable trend over time, with a relatively low range (3.28-5.21) and a mean of 5.07. The mean of environmental diplomacy (ED) is 1.57, with zero being the lowest and 4.20 being the highest, which is unevenly distributed. GDP has a high average (8.47) and that reflects a high level of economic activity, whereas environmental policy stringency (EPS) has the lowest mean (0.52), which represents rather moderate and general policy implementation across the sample. Table 2, below, provides the Pearson correlation. CO₂PI is positively correlated with FG (0.05), ED (0.15), GDP (0.29), and EPS (0.05) with weak positive correlations implying that environmental pressure is only weakly related to financial,

economic, and policy-related variables. FG is positively correlated with EPS (0.94), which means that a greater financial globalization is significantly related to stringent environmental policies. On the contrary, ED has negative relationships with FG (-0.38) and EPS (-0.37), which implies that higher environmental diplomacy can be accompanied by less financial integration and stricter policies. GDP has moderate positive relationships with FG (0.23) and EPS (0.34), implying that an economic growth process is more likely to be accompanied by enhanced financial integration, as well as environmental regulations. Correlation analysis, as recommended by Bilal et al.(2024), is necessary to identify the existence of multicollinearity problems ahead of regression estimation, especially when the correlation coefficients are beyond the level of 0.95. In this study, all correlation values remain below this critical level, confirming the absence of severe multicollinearity among the explanatory variables and supporting the reliability of subsequent econometric analyses.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics and Correlation Matrix

Variables	CO ₂ PI	FG	ED	GDP	EPS
Mean	3.24	5.07	1.57	8.47	0.52
Median	2.34	5.10	1.61	8.97	0.63
Maximum	8.32	5.21	4.20	11.24	1.07
Minimum	0.26	3.28	0.00	5.32	-0.33

Correlation Matrix					
CO ₂ PI	1				
FG	0.05	1			
ED	0.15	-0.38	1		
GDP	0.29	0.23	0.11	1	
EPS	0.05	0.94	-0.37	0.34	1

Cross-sectional dependence and slope heterogeneity results

In the context of the present study, the Breusch and Pagan Lagrange Multiplier (LM) test, proposed by Breusch and Pagan (1980), was used in order to remove possible difficulties due to vague or unreliable results in testing cross-section dependence (CD). The results presented in Table 3 clearly indicate that the null hypothesis of no CD is rejected at 1%. Hence, the panel data studied presents a grave problem of CD. Following the identification of CD among the variables under investigation, the cross-sectional

Homogeneity of the slope coefficients was evaluated by using the method of Pesaran and Yamagata (2008). As discussed in Table 4, the study also revealed that the slope of the model in question is heterogeneous rather than homogeneous. As mentioned by Park et al. (2018), the panel data were combined across numerous cross-sections with different institutional structures, cultural differences, and the unique features of each country. In turn, this leads to the possibility of CD, which can produce biased and spurious results.

Table 3: Cross-sectional dependence test

Variables	BP LM	PS LM	BCS LM	PCD
CO ₂ PI	1511.540* (0.0000)	77.705* (0.0000)	78.380* (0.0000)	9.814* (0.0000)
FG	3705.647* (0.0000)	223.647* (0.0000)	220.432* (0.0000)	71.718* (0.0000)
ED	531.891* (0.0000)	19.941* (0.0000)	16.636* (0.0000)	15.124* (0.0000)
GDP	2782.615* (0.0000)	166.261* (0.0000)	159.806* (0.0000)	52.196* (0.0000)
EPS	3481.00* (0.0000)	229.647* (0.0000)	223.432* (0.0000)	62.788* (0.0000)

NOTE: BP LM: Breusch–Pagan LM test; PS LM: Pesaran Scaled LM; BCS LM: Bias-Corrected Scale; PCD: Pesaran CD test; * represents 1% significance level; p-values are in parenthesis

Table 4: Slope heterogeneity test

	Δ	Δ Adjusted
Model	-6.788* (0.000)	-8.614* (0.000)

NOTE: * represents significance level at 1%; p-values are in parenthesis

Unit root results

Table 5 shows the outcome of second-generation panel unit root tests, namely the CIPS and CADF tests, in order to determine the stationarity of the variables. The results show that there is a combination of orders of integration

with a few variables stationary at level I(0) and others attaining stationarity by initially differencing I(1).

Specifically, FG and ED are stationary at level I(0), implying that they do not contain unit roots. In contrast, CO₂PI, GDP, and EPS are non-

stationary at their levels but become stationary after first differencing, confirming their I(1) nature. This mixed order of integration justifies the application of the CS-ARDL (Cross-Sectionally Augmented Autoregressive

Distributed Lag) approach, enabling the estimation of both short-run and long-run relationships among the variables in the study.

Table 5: Panel unit root test results

Variables	CIPS		CADF		Order of Integration
	Level	Δ	Level	Δ	
CO ₂ PI	-0.54	-7.27*	-1.11	-5.17**	I(1)
FG	-6.06*	---	-4.89**	---	I(0)
ED	-2.06*	---	-4.12***	---	I(0)
GDP	-0.68	-1.07**	-0.04	-4.44***	I(1)
EPS	-2.46	-5.18*	-2.46	-6.48*	I(1)

Note: *, **, and *** represents 1 %, 5 %, and 10 % levels of significance

Cointegration results

The next objective is the estimation of the long-run relations among the variables of interest. Towards that end, we employed a range of cointegration tests, developed by Pedroni (2004) and Westerlund (2007). In the Pedroni tests, the results are reported in Table 6; it is here that six out of eleven statistics gave statistically significant values, thereby confirming a long-run

relationship. Additionally, the Westerlund tests have been performed in order to further substantiate these empirical findings that confirm the existence of cointegration between the variables. In summary, therefore, both methodologies of testing support the existence of a long-term cointegration among the variables.

Table 6: Padroni and Westerlund Cointegration tests

Pedroni				
	Statistic	p-Value	Within Weight	p-Value
Within dimension				
Panel v-Statistic	-4.853	1.0000	-5.018	1.000
Panel rho-Statistic	1.363	0.9282	2.070	0.9803
Panel PP-Statistic	-3.881	0.0001*	-1.771	0.0453**
Panel ADF-Statistic	-7.644	0.0000*	-1.414	0.0433**
Between dimensions				
Group rho-Statistic	2.704	0.895		
Group PP-Statistic	-1.212	0.038**		
Group ADF-Statistic	-2.139	0.016**		
Westerlund				
	18.481	0.0000*		

Note: * and ** represents 1 % and 5 % levels of significance

Long-run and Short-run estimates of CS-ARDL

Table 7 reports the long-run and short-run estimates obtained from the CS-ARDL (2,2,2,2,2) model, with the CO₂ Pressure Index (CO₂PI) as the dependent variable.

From the long-run perspective, Financial Globalization (FG) exerts a positive and statistically significant effect on CO₂PI, with a coefficient of 1.31, indicating that higher levels of financial globalization contribute to increased carbon-related environmental pressure in the long term. Environmental Diplomacy (ED) also shows a positive and significant association with CO₂PI (coefficient = 2.39), suggesting that greater diplomatic engagement on environmental matters does not necessarily translate into lower carbon pressure, possibly due to implementation or coordination inefficiencies. On the same note, CO₂PI is positively affected with a strong coefficient of 0.57 by economic growth, which means that an increase in economic activity increases the carbon pressure. There is a strong positive long-term impact of EPS (coefficient = 5.23), which suggests that more stringent environmental regulation can be positively related to an increase in CO₂ pressure, which in turn could be due to compliance costs, rebounds, or enforcement constraints. Nevertheless, the interaction term (EPS x FG) has a negative and large coefficient (-1.72), indicating that globalization of finances moderates the negative

effect of policy stringency on carbon pressure in the long-run. Financial Globalization has a substantial negative impact on CO₂PI in the short-run dynamics (coefficient = -2.04), meaning that financial integration initially assists in decreasing the carbon pressure, but this effect is reversed in the long term. There are statistically insignificant short-run impacts of Environmental Diplomacy and GDP, which means that the impacts of these variables on CO₂ pressure manifest themselves more in the long-term than in the short-term. Contrary to this fact, Environmental Policy Stringency bears a negative and significant short-run effect (coefficient = -6.23), which shows that tight policy is effective in reducing carbon pressure in the short-run. The interaction term (D(EPS x FG) is positive and significant (coefficient = 2.79), which means that financial globalization can undermine the short-term performance of the environmental regulations. The error correction term, ECM (-1), has a negative value, which is statistically significant (-0.31) and it proves that there is a stable long-run equilibrium relationship between the variables. This coefficient implies that short-run disequilibrium in CO₂ pressure is corrected at a relatively moderate rate, i.e., about 31% per period, so there is a relatively moderate speed at which the long-run equilibrium is attained.

Table 7: Long-run and Short-run estimates of CS-ARDL

Dependent Variable: CO ₂ PI (2,2,2,2,2)				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. error	t-stat	p-value
Long-run coefficients				
FG	1.31	0.39	3.36*	0.00
ED	2.39	1.24	1.93*	0.00
GDP	0.57	0.06	9.50*	0.00
EPS	5.23	1.31	3.99*	0.00
EPS*FG	-1.72	0.49	-3.51*	0.00
Short-run coefficients				
D(FG)	-2.04	0.44	-4.64*	0.00
D(ED)	0.02	0.02	1.00	0.36
D(GDP)	0.39	0.43	0.91	0.20
D(EPS)	-6.23	3.16	-1.97**	0.02

D(EPS*FG)	2.79	0.69	4.04**	0.03
ECM(-1)	-0.31	0.08	-3.88*	0.00

Note: * and ** represents 1 % and 5 %, levels of significance

Causality results

The causal results of Dumitrescu and Hurlin's panel indicate that there are some crucial causal relationships between the variables. There is a solid two-way causal relationship between Financial Globalization (FG) and the CO2 Pressure Index (CO2PI), which implies that there is a bi-directional causation between financial integration and carbon pressure. CO2PI is not driven by Environmental Diplomacy (ED), but unidirectionally, ED is driven by CO2PI, indicating that an increase in carbon pressure can

elicit a diplomatic response on environmental matters. It has a weak two-way relationship between GDP and CO2PI, which indicates a two-sided relationship between carbon pressure and economic growth. Also, both Environmental Policy Stringency (EPS) and the interaction term (EPS x FG) have unidirectional causality to CO2PI, which underscores the overwhelming influence of environmental policies in the dynamics of financial globalization to create carbon pressure.

Table 8: Dumitrescu and Hurlin panel causality results

Null Hypothesis	W-stat	Zbar-stat	p-value	Causality
FG → CO2PI	6.81	7.23	5.e-10*	Bi-directional
CO2PI → FG	3.14	1.99	0.0579***	
ED → CO2PI	4.94	1.26	0.24	Uni-directional
CO2PI → ED	6.67	6.80	6.e-09*	
GDP → CO2PI	4.21	1.65	0.06***	Bi-directional
CO2PI → GDP	3.22	1.51	0.08***	
EPS → CO2PI	8.86	13.82	0.00*	Uni-directional
CO2PI → EPS	2.35	0.48	0.56	
EPS*FG → CO2PI	11.09	14.05	0.00*	Uni-directional
CO2PI → EPS*FG	2.30	0.92	0.40	

Note: * and *** represents 1 % and 10 % levels of significance

Discussion

The study results identify complex links between financial globalization (FG), environmental policies (EPS), economic growth (GDP) and environmental performance (CO2PI). Research data verifies that all these elements form a connected network that affects ecological sustainability through combined direct and indirect effects. The long-term effects of financial globalization and economic development on CO2PI exist; nevertheless, their positive and negative consequences cannot be determined easily. Financial globalization (FG), along with economic development (ED), applies force on ecological resources, which results in

environmental degradation. Global economic integration initially puts pressure on natural resources, due to which environmental concerns about reckless financial expansion emerge. The adverse consequences of financial globalization are counterbalanced by the strong environmental policies that guarantee the proper management of resources amid the success of globalization as a tool of sustainability.

Financial and environmental reforms lead to short-run costs of adjustment. Financial globalization and economic growth have early negative impacts on CO2PI as rapid financial integration and economic growth bring about transitory environmental pressure. The presence

of a fundamental error correction mechanism (ECM) is an indication that, with the environmental policies in place and appropriately implemented, the threat of the negative impact of financial globalization is swiftly corrected. Good environmental governance is a significant factor since it facilitates consistent ecological performance after the short-term environmental disruptions as a result of financial liberalization.

This critical finding of the cause-and-effect analysis indicates that the environmental laws are the key driver of the CO₂PI that demonstrates that correct regulatory measures manage the environmental performance over long durations. The two-way relationship that financial openness generates with CO₂PI is that environmental advancement assists in setting up financial policies of green investments and sustainable economic operations. The interaction effect between GDP and CO₂PI works both ways since economic development encourages environmental investments, but uncontrolled growth generates more environmental harm. Findings of the research contribute to broad knowledge that economic growth must liberate itself from adverse environmental effects to attain sustainable environmental results.

6. Conclusion

The Carbon Pressure Index model explains the effects of Financial Globalization (FG), Economic Development (ED), Gross Domestic Product (GDP) and the Environmental Policy Stringency (EPS) on environmental degradation. According to long term results, FG, ED, and GDP have a positive effect on CO₂PI, which points to the fact that economic and financial growth can cause environmental degradation. Conversely, the negative relationship between FG and EPS is an indication that there is a possibility of inefficiencies, which may result in cases where financial integration takes place without proper environmental regulations. This highlights the significance of the multifaceted policies that would tie financial globalization to strict environmental controls to address the possible ecological problems. The error correction model (ECM) discloses the adjustment speed of -0.31,

pointing out that about 31 percent of the adjustment of disequilibrium happens within some period. It represents a moderate level of convergence in which the performance of the environment tends to stabilize after temporary changes or a policy. The results confirm that CO₂PI is robust to external shocks, i.e., financial crises or changes in regulations and the system gradually stabilizes. The approximate period of adjustment indicates that it is possible to re-establish balance in environmental governance policies, assuming the reformative action programs are taken. These findings lay stress on the importance of environmental policies in the balancing of financial globalization, economic growth, and environmental sustainability. The positive relation between FG and EPS is short-term, and it means that the pressures related to globalization can be reduced successfully through a properly designed regulation. Nevertheless, the results of the long-term analysis highlight the importance of the continuous process of policy enhancement to protect the ecological integrity in the context of financial growth. In conclusion, the study reveals the paramount need to reconcile economic and financial policies with environmental policies to enable sustainable management of the resources so that economic progress and globalization cannot be at odds with the long-term environmental objectives.

6.1 Policy Implications:

The findings of this discussion reveal the importance of a coherent incorporation of financial globalization, economic development, and environmental sustainability. Financial globalization and economic growth may pose significant pressure on the ecological resources, yet the effects of such negative effects may be mitigated by the introduction of strong environmental regulations, thus enabling globalization to become the tool of sustainable resource management. The negative long-term correlation between GDP and CO₂PI is viewed as a negative indicator of the urgent necessity to decouple economic progress and environmental degradation by encouraging the adoption of green finance, circular economy, and shifts to

clean energy. Furthermore, the results of the error correction model show that the adjustment process can be rather rapid and, therefore, the existence of properly designed regulatory measures can benefit the environmental performance even in the case of short-term disruptions. That is why it is so crucial that the policies should be proactive and flexible enough to balance the need to develop the economy with the need to preserve the ecology and allow the transition to sustainability.

Policymakers must therefore leverage financial globalization as an opportunity to drive green investments through the implementation of sustainability-based financial policies, ESG-based capital allocation, and strict compliance schemes to synchronize the economic and environmental goals. The positive correlation between the extent of financial globalization and the strictness of environmental policies signifies that the negative impact of financial globalization can be abated by a strict set of environmental policies, thus realizing the freedom of financial flows and ecological integrity. Also, the governments should focus on improving institutional governance, enhancing environmental diplomacy, and encouraging international cooperation in the G20 context to prevent regulatory arbitrage and create unified global sustainable standards. The strong environmental policies should be incorporated into the financial and economic systems to achieve a healthy coexistence between globalization and environmental care. Adoption of powerful environmental policies in financial and economic systems will help nations to achieve a sustainable balance between globalization, economic growth and lasting ecological stability.

6.2 Limitations and Suggestions for Future Research:

The study has limitations of differences in data quality across countries, a very specific focus on the G20 countries, and exclusion of nonlinear effects or outside shocks like an economic recession or geopolitical tensions. In addition, the emphasis laid on macroeconomic indicators does not consider the microeconomic factors,

like the sustainability projects of firms and technological developments, which also contribute to a considerable extent towards defining environmental outcomes. Further research needs to be conducted to explore nonlinear interactions using the advanced econometric tools, extend the analysis to less-developed countries and conduct industry-specific analyses to identify the environmental impacts that are specific to different industries. Enhancing the precision of such predictions, including measurements of climate risks, indicators of biodiversity decline, and instant simulations of policy outcomes, would add value to the concept, thus helping policy makers to develop adaptive and proactive sustainability frameworks.

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